

-SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES-

Multi-locus phylogenetic analyses uncover species boundaries and reveal the occurrence of two new entomopathogenic nematode species, *Heterorhabditis ruandica* n. sp. and *Heterorhabditis zacatecana* n. sp.

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Table S1. Origin of the nematodes used in this study

Nematode species	Isolate	Reference
<i>H. ruandica</i>	Rw18_M-Hr1a	Fallet et al., 2020
<i>H. ruandica</i>	Rw18_M-Hr1b	
<i>H. ruandica</i>	Rw14_N-C4a	Yan et al., 2016
<i>H. zacatecana</i>	MEX-39	Bruno et al., 2020
<i>H. zacatecana</i>	MEX-40	
<i>H. zacatecana</i>	MEX-41	
<i>H. atacamensis</i>	MEX-20	
<i>H. bacteriophora</i>	DE2	Mukuka et al., 2010; Carrera, 2015
	DE6	
	PT1	
	IT6	
	EN01	
	TT01	Bai et al., 2013
	CH21	Rana et al., 2020
<i>H. beicherriana</i>	H06	Han (1996)
<i>H. georgiana</i>	Hbb	Bruce Hibbard (Unpublished)
<i>H. indica</i>	CH7	Bhat et al., 2021b

Table S2. Sequences of the primers used to amplify the genes/genetic regions of different *Heterorhabditis* species used for the phylogenetic analyses in this study.

Genetic region	Primers	Orientation	Sequence 5' to 3'	Description
ITS	TW81	F	GTTTCCGTAGGTGAACCTGC	Joyce et al. (1994)
	AB28	R	ATATGCTTAAGTTCAGCGGGT	
D2-D3	D2A	F	ACAAGTACCGTGAGGGAAAGTTG	Subbotin et al. (2006)
	D3B	R	TCGGAAGGAACCAGCTACTA	
COI	HCF	F	TTACATGATACTTATTATG	Kuwata et al. (2007)
	HCR	R	CTGATAACTGTGACCAAATACATA	
cmd-1	cmd1F	F	GGATACTGACAGTGAAGA	Regeai et al. (2009)
	cmd1R	R	CTCTCCCAGATTCGTCATTAC	
unc-87	unc87F	F	GGA ACTCCCAGGAACACCAGC	
	unc87R	R	CGTTCCTGACTGAAGGCGGAC	

Table S3. National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) accession numbers of the nucleotide sequences used for the phylogenetic analyses in this study. In bold font are the sequences (75 in total) newly generated in this study.

Organism		Genetic Region				
Species	Strain designation (s)	ITS	D2-D3	COI	cmd-1	unc-87
<i>H. amazonensis</i>	CD2510, MC01	MT372499	MT372502	MT372499	MT406142	MT375792
<i>H. atacamensis</i>	MEX-20	MK421485	MW817561	MW817979	MW827770	MW827756
<i>H. bacteriophora</i>	DE2	MZ326036	MW817552	MW817970	MW827763	MW827748
	DE6	MZ326037	MW817553	MW817971	MW827764	MW827749
	EN01	MZ326038	MW817554	MW817972	MW827765	MW827750
	IT6	MZ326039	MW817555	MW817973	MW827766	MW827751
	PT1	MZ326040	MW817556	MW817974	MW827767	MW827752
	TT01	MZ326041	MW817557	MW817975	MW827768	MW827753
	CD2504, HP88	MT372491	MT372509	MT373729	MT406138	MT375796
<i>H. baujardi</i>	CD2519, F10	MT372500	MT372503	MT373736	MT406139	MT375791
<i>H. beicherriana</i>	H06	MZ326043	MW817560	MW817978	MZ325342	-
	CD2516, QZL-2011	MT372490	MT372511	MT373730	-	MT375797
<i>H. downesi</i>	CD2508, 23.9	MT372494	MT372507	MT373732	MT406135	MT375794
<i>H. floridensis</i>	CD2503, K22	MT372501	MT372504	MT373737	MT406141	MT375793
<i>H. georgiana</i>	Hbb	MZ326042	MW817558	MW817976	MW827769	MW827754
	CD2500	MT372492	MT372510	MT373731	-	MT375798
	No information	-	-	-	EU685891	-
<i>H. indica</i>	CD2525	MT372498	-	-	-	-
	MEX-10	-	MK421439	-	-	-
	LN2	-	-	AB355853	-	EU685888
	CH7	-	-	-	MZ325341	-
<i>H. marelatus</i>	OH10	AY321479	-	-	-	-
	No information	-	EU100412	-	-	-
	No information	-	-	EF043419	-	-
	BOD	-	-	-	-	EU685884
<i>H. megidis</i>	CD2518, DV	MT372495	MT372506	MT373733	MT406136	MT375795
<i>H. mexicana</i>	Mexican	AY321478	-	-	-	-
	MX	-	EU100414	-	-	-
	No information	-	-	EF043422	-	-
	MX4	-	-	-	EU685895	EU685887
<i>H. noenieputensis</i>	CD2506, SF669	MT372497	MT372505	MT373728	-	-
<i>H. ruandica</i> n. sp.	Rw18_M-Hr1a	MZ326033	MW817549	MW817967	MW827760	MW827745
	Rw18_M-Hr1b	MZ326034	MW817550	MW817968	MW827761	MW827746
	Rw14_N-C4a	MZ326035	MW817551	MW817969	MW827762	MW827747
<i>H. safricana</i>	No information	EF488006	EU100416	-	-	-
<i>H. taysearae</i>	Gbabe138a	MF372596	-	-	-	-
	No information	-	-	EF043421	-	-
	PAL H04	-	-	-	EU685894	EU685886
<i>H. zacatecana</i> n. sp.	MEX-39	MZ326030	MW817546	MW817964	MW827757	MW827742
	MEX-40	MZ326031	MW817547	MW817965	MW827758	MW827743
	MEX-41	MZ326032	MW817548	MW817966	MW827759	MW827744
<i>H. zealandica</i>	CD2507	MT372493	MT372508	MT373734	MT406137	-

Table S4. National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) accession numbers of the sequences used in this study.

	Accession numbers
<i>P. aegyptia</i> BA1 ^T	JFGV01
<i>P. akhurstii</i> DSM 15138 ^T	RCWE01
<i>P. asymbiotica</i> DSM 15149 ^T	RBLJ01
<i>P. australis</i> subsp. <i>australis</i> DSM 17609 ^T	JONO01
<i>P. australis</i> subsp. <i>thailandensis</i> PB68.1 ^T	LOMY01
<i>P. bodei</i> LJ24-63 ^T	NSCM01
<i>P. caribbeanensis</i> DSM 22391 ^T	RCWB01
<i>P. cinerea</i> DSM 19724 ^T	PUJW01
<i>P. hainanensis</i> DSM 22397 ^T	RCWD01
<i>P. heterorhabditis</i> subsp. <i>heterorhabditis</i> SF41 ^T	RCWA01
<i>P. heterorhabditis</i> subsp. <i>aluminescens</i> Q614 ^T	JABBCS01
<i>P. khanii</i> subsp. <i>khanii</i> DSM 3369 ^T	AYSJ01
<i>P. khanii</i> subsp. <i>guanajuatensis</i> MEX20-17 ^T	PUJY01
<i>P. kleinii</i> S8-52	NSCL01
<i>P. kleinii</i> S9-53	NSCK01
<i>P. kleinii</i> S10-54	NSCJ01
<i>P. laumondii</i> subsp. <i>clarkei</i> BOJ-47 ^T	NSCI01
<i>P. laumondii</i> subsp. <i>laumondii</i> TT01 ^T	WSFH01
<i>P. laumondii</i> subsp. <i>laumondii</i> S12-55	NSCH01
<i>P. laumondii</i> subsp. <i>laumondii</i> S14-60	NSCE01
<i>P. laumondii</i> subsp. <i>laumondii</i> S15-56	NSCF0
<i>P. laumondii</i> subsp. <i>laumondii</i> RW14-46	PUJT01
<i>P. luminescens</i> subsp. <i>luminescens</i> ATCC 29999 ^T	FMWJ01
<i>P. luminescens</i> subsp. <i>mexicana</i> MEX47-22 ^T	PUJX01
<i>P. namnaonensis</i> PB45.5 ^T	LOIC01
<i>P. noenieputensis</i> DSM 25462 ^T	RCWC01
<i>P. stackebrandtii</i> DSM 23271 ^T	PUJV01
<i>P. tasmaniensis</i> DSM 22387 ^T	PUJU01
<i>P. thracensis</i> DSM 15199 ^T	CP011104